

On decomposition of $n\check{g}$ -continuity in nano Topological spaces

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Abstract: This article focuses on decomposition of a weaker form of nano continuity, namely $n\check{g}$ -continuity, by providing the concepts of $n\check{g}_t$ -sets, $n\check{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -sets, $n\check{g}_t$ -continuity and $n\check{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -continuity.

Key words: $n\check{g}_{\alpha}$ -closed, $n\check{g}_p$ -closed, $n\check{g}_t$ s, $n\check{g}_{\alpha^*}$ s

1. Introduction

Various interesting problems arise when one considers nano continuous (in short, n-cts) and nano generalized continuous (in short, ng-cts). Decomposition of n-cts are obtained by many mathematician with the help of ng-cts maps in nano topological spaces (in short, ntss)([5, 6, 19]). This article, we obtained decomposition of $n\check{g}$ -continuous (in short, $n\check{g}$ -cts) in ntss using $n\check{g}_p$ -continuous (in short, $n\check{g}_p$ -cts) [20], $n\check{g}_{\alpha}$ -continuous (in short, $n\check{g}_{\alpha}$ -cts) [20], $n\check{g}_t$ -continuous (in short, $n\check{g}_t$ -cts) and $n\check{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -continuous (in short, $n\check{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts).

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [11] If $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is the ntss with respect to P where $P \subseteq K$ and if $S \subseteq K$, then

1. The nano interior of the set S is defined as the union of all nano open (in short, no) subsets contained in S and it is denoted by $n\text{inte}(S)$. That is, $n\text{inte}(S)$ is the largest no subset of S.
2. The nano closure of the set S is defined as the intersection of all nano closed (in short, nc)sets containing S and it is denoted by $n\text{clo}(S)$. That is, $n\text{clo}(S)$ is the smallest nc set containing S.

Definition 2.2. [11] A subset S of a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is said to be

1. nano α -closed (in short, $n\alpha c$) if $n\text{clo}(n\text{inte}(n\text{clo}(S))) \subseteq S$.
2. nano semi-closed (in short, nsc) if $n\text{inte}(n\text{clo}(S)) \subseteq S$.
3. nano pre-closed (in short, npc) if $n\text{clo}(n\text{inte}(S)) \subseteq S$.

The complements of the above mentioned nc are called their respective no respectively.

The nano α -closure [18] (respectively, nano semi-closure [2, 3], nano pre-closure [1]) of a subset S of K, denoted by $n\alpha\text{clo}(S)$ (respectively. $n\text{sclo}(S)$, $n\text{pclo}(S)$) is defined to be the intersection of all $n\alpha c$ (respectively. nsc, npc) sets of $(K, \tau_R(P))$ containing S.

The nano α -interior [18] (respectively, nano semi-interior [2, 3], nano pre-interior[1]) of a subset S of K, denoted by $n\alpha\text{inte}(S)$ (respectively. $\text{nsinte}(S)$, $\text{npinte}(S)$) is defined to be the union of all $n\alpha o$ (respectively. nso , npo) sets of $(K, \tau_R(P))$ containing S.

Definition 2.3. A subset S of a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is called :

1. nsg-open (in short, nsgo) [2] if $T \subseteq \text{nsinte}(S)$ whenever $T \subseteq S$ and T is nano semi-closed in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.
2. $\text{n}\ddot{g}\text{-open}$ (in short, $\text{n}\ddot{g}o$) [18] if $T \subseteq \text{ninte}(S)$ whenever $T \subseteq S$ and T is nsg-closed in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.
3. $\text{n}\ddot{g}_\alpha\text{-open}$ (in short, $\text{n}\ddot{g}_\alpha o$) [18] if $T \subseteq n\alpha\text{inte}(S)$ whenever $T \subseteq S$ and T is nsg-closed in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.
4. $\text{n}\ddot{g}_p\text{-open}$ (in short, $\text{n}\ddot{g}_p o$) [20] if $T \subseteq \text{npinte}(S)$ whenever $T \subseteq S$ and T is nsg-closed in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.

The complement of above mentioned no-sets are called their respective nc-sets.

Definition 2.4. A subset S of a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is said to be

1. nt-set (in short, nts) [10] if $\text{ninte}(S) = \text{ninte}(\text{nclo}(S))$.
2. $n\alpha^*\text{-set}$ (in short, $n\alpha^*s$) [16] if $\text{ninte}(S) = \text{ninte}(\text{nclo}(\text{inte}(S)))$.
3. an $n\eta$ -set [8] if $S = I \cap J$ where I is no & J is a $n\alpha c$.
4. $n\eta^\#$ -set (in short, $n\eta^\#s$) [19] if $S = I \cap J$, where I is nsgo & J is $n\alpha c$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.
5. $n\eta^{\#\#}$ -set (in short, $n\eta^{\#\#}s$) [19] if $S = I \cap J$, where I is $\text{n}\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ & J is nts in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.
6. $\text{n}\ddot{g}lc^*\text{-set}$ (in short, $\text{n}\ddot{g}lc^*s$) [20] if $S = I \cap J$, where I is nsgo & J is nc $(K, \tau_R(P))$

Collection of all $n\eta s$ (respectively, $n\eta^\#s$, $n\eta^{\#\#}s$) in a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is denoted by $n\eta(K, \tau_R(P))$ (respectively, $n\eta^\#(K, \tau_R(P))$, $n\eta^{\#\#}(K, \tau_R(P))$).

Remark 2.1. $n\alpha c$ sets and $\text{n}\ddot{g}c$ sets are independent.

Example 2.1. Let $K = \{11, 12, 13\}$ with $K / R = \{\{13\}, \{11, 12\}, \{12, 11\}\}$ and $P = \{11, 12\}$, $\tau_R(P) = \{\phi, \{11, 12\}, K\}$. Here, the set $\{12, 13\}$ is $\text{n}\ddot{g}c$ but not $n\alpha c$.

2. Let $K = \{11, 12, 13\}$ with $K / R = \{\{11\}, \{12, 13\}\}$ and $P = \{11\}$, $\tau_R(P) = \{\phi, \{11\}, K\}$. Here, the set $\{12\}$ is $n\alpha c$ but not $\text{n}\ddot{g}c$.

Remark 2.2. [16]

1. Every nts is an $n\alpha^*s$ but not conversely.
2. Union of 2 $n\alpha^*s$ need not be an $n\alpha^*s$.
3. Intersection of 2 $n\alpha^*s$ is an $n\alpha^*s$.

Definition 2.5. A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is called:

1. n-cts [12] if $f^{-1}(D)$ is a no in $(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
2. $n\alpha\text{-continuous}$ (in short, $n\alpha\text{-cts}$) [13] if $f^{-1}(D)$ is $n\alpha o$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.

3. $n\ddot{g}$ -cts [20] if $f^{-1}(D)$ is $n\ddot{g}o$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
4. $n\ddot{g}_\alpha$ -cts [20](respectively, $n\ddot{g}_p$ -cts [20]) if $f^{-1}(D)$ is $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ (respectively. $n\ddot{g}_p o$) set in $(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
5. $n\ddot{g}lc^*$ -continuous (in short, $n\ddot{g}lc^*$ -cts) [20] if $f^{-1}(D) \in n\ddot{g}lc^*(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
6. $n\eta^\#$ -continuous (in short, $n\eta^\#$ -cts) [18] if $f^{-1}(D) \in n\eta^\#(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
7. $n\eta^{\#\#}$ -continuous (in short, $n\eta^{\#\#}$ -cts) [18] if $f^{-1}(D) \in n\eta^{\#\#}(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.

Theorem 2.1. [20] *A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is n -cts iff it is both $n\ddot{g}$ -cts and $n\ddot{g}lc^*$ -cts.*

Theorem 2.2. [19]

1. *A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is $n\alpha$ -cts iff it is both $n\ddot{g}_\alpha$ -cts and $n\eta^\#$ -cts.*
2. *A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is $n\ddot{g}_\alpha$ -cts iff it is both $n\ddot{g}_p$ -cts and $n\eta^{\#\#}$ -cts.*

3. $n\ddot{g}_t s$ & $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$

Definition 3.1. A subset H of a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is said to be

1. an $n\ddot{g}_t$ -sets (in short, $n\ddot{g}_t s$) if $H = I \cap J$, where I is $n\ddot{g}o$ in K & J is a nts in K .
2. an $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^*$ -sets (in short, $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$) if $H = I \cap J$, where I is $n\ddot{g}o$ in K & J is a $n\alpha^* s$ in K .

Collection of all $n\ddot{g}_t s$ (respectively, $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$) in a ntss $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is denoted by $n\ddot{g}_t(K, \tau_R(P))$ (respectively, $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^*(K, \tau_R(P))$).

Proposition 3.1. *Let H be a subset of K . Then*

1. *if H is a nts , then $H \in n\ddot{g}_t(K, \tau_R(P))$.*
2. *if H is an $n\alpha^* s$, then $H \in n\ddot{g}_\alpha^*(K, \tau_R(P))$.*
3. *if H is an $n\ddot{g}o$ set in K , then $H \in n\ddot{g}_t(K, \tau_R(P))$ & $H \in n\ddot{g}_\alpha^*(K, \tau_R(P))$.*

Proof. The proof is straightforward from the definitions. □

Proposition 3.2. *In a ntss K , every $n\ddot{g}_t s$ is an $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$ but not conversely.*

Proof. The proof is straightforward from the definitions. □

Example 3.1. *Let K and $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, the set $\{11, 13\}$ is $n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$ but not $n\ddot{g}_t s$.*

Remark 3.1. *The following examples show that*

1. *the converse of Proposition 3.1 need not be true.*
2. *$n\ddot{g}_t s$ & $n\ddot{g}_p o$ sets are independent.*
3. *$n\ddot{g}_\alpha^* s$ & $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ sets are independent.*

Example 3.2. Let K & $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, the set $\{11\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ but not a $n\check{t} s$ & the set $\{11, 12\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ but not $n\alpha^* s$.

Example 3.3. Let K & $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, the set $\{13\}$ is both $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ & $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ but not $\check{n}\check{g}_o$ set.

Example 3.4. Let K & $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, (a) the set $\{13\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ but not a $\check{n}\check{g}_p o$, (b) the set $\{12, 13\}$ is a $\check{n}\check{g}_p o$ set but not $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$.

Example 3.5. Let $K = \{11, 12, 13, 14\}$ with $K / R = \{\{11\}, \{12, 13\}, \{12, 14\}\}$ and $P = \{11\}$, $\tau_R(P) = \{\phi, \{11\}, K\}$. Here, (a) the set $\{12\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ but not $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha o$, (b) the set $\{11, 13\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha o$ but not $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$.

Example 3.6. Let K & $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, the set $\{11\}$ is $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ and $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ but it is not $\check{n}\check{g}_c$.

Remark 3.2. From the above discussions and known results in [[14], [18], [20]], we obtained the following diagram where $A \rightarrow B$ represents A implies B , but not conversely.

Remark 3.3. ,

1. Union of 2 $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ need not be an $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$.
2. Union of 2 $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ need not be an $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$.

Example 3.7. ,

1. Let K and $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 2.1(1). Here, the sets are $\{12\}$ and $\{13\}$ are $\check{n}\check{g}_t$ -sets but $\{12\} \cup \{13\} = \{12, 13\}$ is not an $\check{n}\check{g}_t$ -set.
2. Let K and $\tau_R(P)$ in the Example 3.5. Here, the sets are $\{11\}$ and $\{12\}$ are $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^*$ -sets but $\{11\} \cup \{12\} = \{11, 12\}$ is not an $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$.

Remark 3.4. ,

1. Intersection of any 2 $\check{n}\check{g}_t s$ belongs to $\check{n}\check{g}_t (K, \tau_R(P))$.
2. Intersection of any 2 of $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* s$ belongs to $\check{n}\check{g}_\alpha^* (K, \tau_R(P))$.

Lemma 3.1. ,

1. A subset H of $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is $n\ddot{g}o$ [18] iff $F \subseteq ninte(H)$ whenever $F \subseteq H$ and F is $nsgc$ in K .
2. A subset H of $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ [20] iff $F \subseteq n\alpha inte(H)$ whenever $F \subseteq H$ and F is $nsgc$ in K .
3. A subset H of $(K, \tau_R(P))$ is $n\ddot{g}_p o$ [20] iff $F \subseteq npinte(H)$ whenever $F \subseteq H$ and F is $nsgc$ in K .

Theorem 3.1. A subset H is $n\ddot{g}o$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$ iff it is both $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ and $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*s}$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.

Proof. Necessity. Obvious.

Sufficiency. Suppose H be both $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ set and $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*s}$. Since H is an $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*s}$, $H = I \cap J$, where I is $n\ddot{g}o$ and J is an $n\alpha^*s$. Assume that $F \subseteq H$, where F is $nsgc$ in K . Since I is $n\ddot{g}o$, by Lemma 3.1 (1), $F \subseteq ninte(H)$. Since H is $n\ddot{g}_\alpha o$ in K , by Lemma 3.1 (2), $F \subseteq n\alpha inte(H) = H \cap ninte(nclo(ninte(H))) = (I \cap J) \cap ninte(nclo(ninte(I \cap J))) \subseteq I \cap J \cap ninte(nclo(ninte(I))) \cap ninte(nclo(ninte(J))) = I \cap J \cap ninte(nclo(ninte(I))) \cap ninte(J) \subseteq ninte(J)$. Therefore, we obtained $F \subseteq ninte(J)$ and hence $F \subseteq ninte(I) \cap ninte(J) = ninte(H)$. Hence H is $nsgo$, by Lemma 3.1 (1). \square

Theorem 3.2. A subset H is $n\ddot{g}o$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$ iff it is both $n\ddot{g}_p o$ and $n\ddot{g}_t s$ in $(K, \tau_R(P))$.

Proof. The proof is similar to theorem 3.1. \square

Definition 3.2. A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is said to be

1. $n\ddot{g}_t$ -cts if $f^{-1}(D) \in n\ddot{g}_t(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.
2. $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts if $f^{-1}(D) \in n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*}(K, \tau_R(P))$, for every no set D of $(L, \sigma_R(Q))$.

Theorem 3.3. For a map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$, the following implications hold:

1. $n\ddot{g}$ -cts \Rightarrow $n\ddot{g}_t$ -cts.
2. $n\ddot{g}$ -cts \Rightarrow $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts.
3. $n\ddot{g}_t$ -cts is an $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts.
4. $n\ddot{g}$ -cts \Rightarrow $n\ddot{g}_\alpha$ -cts \Rightarrow $n\ddot{g}_p$ -cts. [20]

Proof. (1) and (2). The proof is straightforward from the proposition 3.1.

(3). The proof is straightforward from the proposition 3.2. \square

Remark 3.5. ,

1. $n\ddot{g}_t$ -cts and $n\ddot{g}_p$ -cts are independent.
2. $n\ddot{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts and $n\ddot{g}_\alpha$ -cts are independent.

Remark 3.6.

We obtained some dcomposition of $n\tilde{g}$ -cts

Theorem 3.4. A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is $n\tilde{g}$ -cts iff it is both $n\tilde{g}_\alpha$ -cts and $n\tilde{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts.

Proof. The proof is straightforward from theorem 3.1. □

Theorem 3.5. A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is $n\tilde{g}$ -cts iff it is both $n\tilde{g}_p$ -cts, $n\eta^{\#\#}$ -cts and $n\tilde{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts.

Proof. The proof is straightforward from theorem 2.2 (2) and theorem 3.4. □

Theorem 3.6. A map $f : (K, \tau_R(P)) \rightarrow (L, \sigma_R(Q))$ is $n\tilde{g}$ -cts iff it is both $n\tilde{g}_p$ -cts and $n\tilde{g}_t$ -cts.

Proof. The proof is straightforward from theorem 3.2. □

Conclusion

We obtained decomposition of $n\tilde{g}$ -cts in ntss using $n\tilde{g}_p$ -cts, $n\tilde{g}_\alpha$ -cts, $n\tilde{g}_t$ -cts and $n\tilde{g}_{\alpha^*}$ -cts. The results of this study may be help to many researches.

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